

Relativistic Features In Nonrelativistic Quantum Mechanics

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In previous notes we have argued that nonrelativistic quantum mechanics is a statistical theory based on free quantum particles i.e. momentum probability states as in classical statistical mechanics. We further argued that impulse hits from a potential change a particle from one state into another. The potential $V(x)$, however, is associated with acceleration from x to $x+dx$ and not impulses according to Newton's second law. Thus, the statistical impulse hits must somehow create $V(x)$ on average. We suggested $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ where $\exp(ikx)$ is a complex unnormalized probability. We also suggested the form $\exp(ipx)$ (or a weighted average) for the quantum particle so that $\text{Prob}(\text{particle with } k_1)\text{Prob}(\text{potential with } k_2)$ is proportional to $\text{Prob}(\text{particle with } k_1+k_2)$. A free quantum particle which receives impulse hits changes from one velocity frame to another because mass is constant (nonrelativistic). This is similar to the idea of special relativity and $\exp(-iEt+ikx)$ suggests a signature for a free particle which is Lorentz invariant.

When creating a bound state, however, one does not use $\exp(-iEt)$ for the free particle states $\exp(ikx)$. Time and space are decoupled. One finds that a bound state resonance forms with an energy E_n . The time dependent portion of the wavefunction is $\exp(-iE_n t)$, but what does this mean as there is no overall net momentum as the bound particle is localized? We argue that $\exp(-iE_n t)$ is of a form such that a special relativistic transformation leads to $\exp(-iE_n t + kt)$. K , the momentum, however must have meaning. We suggest it means that the "whole system" i.e. m of the particle, E_n and M of the particle producing $V(x)$ are moving in a quantum manner which does not disrupt the internal resonance E_n . In such a case, E_n must be part of the "mass" of this composite particle which means mass is energy. This is a special relativistic idea which is found in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics for a bound state which becomes a composite particle which in turn is acted on by another potential in a quantum mechanical manner.

Impulse Picture

Classical mechanics for conservative forces utilizes $V(x)$ yielding a force $-dV/dx$ which allows one to follow a particle at $x(t)$ and know $v(t)$ and $a(t)$ (velocity and acceleration). This is deterministic (not statistical) and is not related to impulses. If one were to consider a statistical picture based on a free particle (i.e. a non-accelerating particle which is always in a momentum state as in classical statistical mechanics) time is removed from the problem as in classical statistical mechanics. The free particle has different probabilities to be in different momentum states, but these are complex because one cannot determine the identity of a momentum state which is continuously transforming (due to impulses) with no time reversal balance. Thus, a kind of cycling resonance occurs. The potential itself becomes stochastic or probabilistic and delivers impulse hits i.e. momentum hits. In a probability impulse picture one needs:

$P(\text{particle with momentum } k_1)P(\text{potential with impulse } k_2)$ proportional to $P(\text{particle with } k_1+k_2)$
(1)

Furthermore: $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } P(\text{potential with impulse } k, x) \text{ and } dV/dx = -F \quad ((2))$

A solution to ((1)) and ((2)) is: $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$ with $\exp(ikx)$ representing a quantum particle. No ideas of special relativity are needed for this and $dV/dx = -F$ is strictly nonrelativistic. Condition ((1)), however, is enough to suggest $\exp(ikx)$ and holds both in the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases.

Given $\exp(ikx)$ as the complex probability of a quantum particle, one might ask what happens to this probability in different frames. It seems plausible to extend $\exp(ikx)$ to $\exp(-iEt+ikx)$ to obtain a Lorentz invariant probability signature, but $\exp(-iEt)$ is not used in solving a bound state problem using the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus, one may ask what is the relevance of $\exp(-iEt)$. We consider this question in the next section.

Nonrelativistic Composite Particle Moving in a Potential

It is possible to consider a quantum nonrelativistic particle with mass m receiving impulse hits from $V(x)$ associated with another quantum particle with mass M where $M \gg m$. Nonrelativistic quantum mechanics yields a quantum resonance with energy E_n by using $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ as the wavefunction (i.e. a momentum probability distribution). One sets $\exp(-iEt)$ as the time dependent portion, but otherwise it does not appear.

Given that a free quantum particle is described by $\exp(ikx)$ and is extended to $\exp(-iEt+ikx)$ where $E = k^2/2m$, one may ask why one may not extend $\exp(-iEt)$ from the bound state. There is no overall momentum in this case, however. Still, one may imagine E_n becoming associated with a momentum. In such a case, E_n should be associated with a mass, but nonrelativistically there is no notion of mass being equivalent to energy. Thus, we suggest that nonrelativistic quantum mechanics suggests that mass is energy as E_n should behave like part of a mass if it is to become associated with a momentum. (Note: it is not a kinetic energy, but the energy of a static resonance.)

As a result, one may consider a composite particle with:

$$\text{mass (energy)} = M + m + E_n \quad ((3))$$

provided that impulse hits from a new potential $V_1(x)$, acting on this composite particle, are not able to disrupt the quantum resonance E_n . Physically there could be scenarios in which the resonance E_n is disrupted e.g.

- (1) $V_1(x)$ acts on the composite particle, but is able to knock E_{n1} into E_{n2}
- (2) $V_1(x)$ may change the nature of the quantum resonance between m and M altogether, thus destroying the composite particle in a sense and creating a new system.

Here we consider the case of the E_n being untouched by a $V_1(x)$ acting on the composite particle. In such a case $\exp(-iEt)$ becoming $\exp(-iEt + kt)$ in a Lorentz boost sense is relevant because all energy pieces of the composite particle are now being knocked from one momentum state to another by impulse hits from $V_1(x)$ and E_n is part of the composite mass. Thus, it seems that special relativity is contained in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics. Even if

one wishes to ignore the form $\exp(-iE_n t)$ in a bound state wavefunction (complex momentum probability distribution function), in the case of the formation of composite particle and a $V_1(x)$ which does not disrupt the E_n resonance, one must consider how E_n becomes part of the motion of the composite particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum bound particle is a statistical object which is always in a free momentum state. This state, however, combines with impulse hits from a potential. Neither are discerned by time reversal balance and so probabilities are complex. (For the particle, its interactions with hits from the potential are not time reversal invariant so there is no real $P(p,x)$.) Rather $\exp(ipx)$ allows for an AND probability situation i.e. $P(\text{particle with } k_1)P(\text{potential hit of } k_2)$ proportional to $P(\text{particle with } k_1+k_2)$. At this point no arguments from special relativity have been used although $\exp(ipx)$ is suggestive of the Lorentz invariant form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is an invariant probability signature of the quantum particle momentum state.

Nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, however, seems to point more strongly towards special relativity if one considers a bound nonrelativistic state. In such a case there is a wave function $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but a single average energy E_n which is included as $\exp(-iE_n t)$. One may imagine the case in which a composite particle is created with E_n as a binding energy, m the mass of the quantum particle and M ($M \gg m$) the mass creating $V(x)$. One may introduce another potential $V_1(x)$ which only affects the composite particle without changing the resonance E_n . In such a case, $\exp(-iE_n t)$ suggests the special relativistic form $\exp(-iE_n t + ikx)$. What is the momentum? One may treat E_n as part of mass (binding energy) together with m and M . Thus, nonrelativistic quantum mechanics leads to the special relativistic idea that energy and mass are equivalent. For the composite particle with overall mass $m+M+E_n$, impulse hits from $V_1(x)$ establish another quantum resonance.

References

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